

CRITICAL SUCCESS FACTORS IN AGILE SOFTWARE PROJECT DEVELOPMENT IN SRI LANKA

Kumara, K.A.P.S. R.¹, Kulathunga, K.M.S.D.²

¹*sanjaryuwan56@gmail.com*

²*dushyanthak@sjp.ac.lk*

Introduction

Background of the study

IT systems are very important for today's organizations as most of the organizations depend on those systems heavily. Modern organizations are automated and computerized. Each year, both public sector and private sector organizations invest a huge amount of money in developing software and systems. Software project development cost is very high due to the complexity of a software development process and its management. Those investments are not always worth for them since many software projects fail due to several reasons. On the other hand, some investments give good benefits to the organization (Mohagheghi & Jorgensen 2017). Therefore, it is essential to identify the critical factors that determine the success of a software project.

Problem Statement

Software development industry is faced with many challenges than before. The demand for the software systems and the expectations of the clients also have increased when compared to the previous years. Therefore, the success of a software project development is critical in modern society. Even though, there are many research studies on identifying the critical success factors that determine the success of a software project development in relation to other countries in the world such as, South Africa, Malaysia, Norway etc., there is a lack of research in Sri Lanka in this regard. Therefore, there is a research gap in the area of identifying the critical success factors that determine the success of software development projects in the Sri Lankan context. Therefore, this study is designed to identify the critical success factors that determine the success of software development projects in Sri Lanka.

Research Objectives

This research focused on the following two research objectives.

- To identify the critical success factors that determine the success of agile software project development in Sri Lanka.
- To determine the relationship between identified critical success factors and the success of agile software project development in Sri Lanka.

Methodology

This research used a quantitative approach since it facilitated to get the views of a larger sample and help to generalize the results. The data were collected using a questionnaire which primarily contained questions with a Likert scale. The sample consisted of 121 IT professionals in Sri Lanka. SPSS was used as the primary tool for analyzing data.

Data Analysis

A multiple regression analysis was used to examine the relationships between identified factors and the success of agile software project development and to test the hypotheses accordingly. A summary of hypotheses testing is given below in Table 1. Thus, the findings reveal that the organizational factors, people factors, technology factors, and process factors are critical factors affecting the successful agile software development projects in Sri Lanka. However, project factors were not found to be a critical factor in this process.

Table 1: Summary of Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis	T statistics	P value	Accepted / Rejected
H1: There is a positive association between organizational factors and the success of agile software project development.	2.732	0.007	Accepted
H2: There is a positive association between people factors and the success of agile software project development.	2.176	0.032	Accepted
H3: There is a positive association between technology factors and the success of agile software project development	3.306	0.001	Accepted
H4: There is a positive association between process factors and the success of agile software project development	2.148	0.034	Accepted

H5: There is a positive association between project factors and the success of agile software project development.	1.782	0.077	Rejected
--	-------	-------	----------

Summary and Conclusion

This study was designed to examine the critical success factors of agile software project development in Sri Lanka. The literature review revealed the existence of five such key factors. Those key factors included: organizational factors, people factors, technology factors, process factors, and project factors. Accordingly, a conceptual framework was developed depicting the relationship between those five factors and the success of agile software development projects. Five hypotheses were developed to test the identified relationships between those independent variables and the dependent variable. Multiple regression analysis revealed that organizational factors, people factors, technology factors and process factors have significant effects on the success of agile software development projects and project factors were found to be not significant.

Implications

The findings of this research are useful from both a theoretical and a managerial perspective. The findings add to the existing literature examining the critical factors affecting the success of agile software development projects. Further, the findings help to lessen the research gap existing, especially in the Sri Lankan context.

Apart from this, the findings of this study would be useful for software developing companies. The findings highlight that the companies in the software development utilizing agile software methodology should focus more on organizational factors, people factors, technology factors and process factors to ensure the success of those development projects.

Limitations and Future Research Work

This study is a cross-sectional study where data were collected at one point in time. Therefore, the findings of this research are valid for the considered period. Future research may focus on longitudinal work, which would help to identify the changes of findings over time. Due to time constraints of the study, data could be collected only from 121 respondents. Future researchers can study the views of a larger sample, increasing the generalizability of the results. Further, this study focused on

five key factors affecting the success of agile software development projects. Future researchers can expand this model by incorporating other factors influencing the agile software development process, which were beyond the scope of this study.

References

Chiyangwa, TB 2017, 'Modelling the critical success factors of agile software development projects in South Africa', *South African Journal of Information Management*, vol.17, no.1, pp.1-8.

Chow, T. & Cao, DB 2008, 'A survey study of critical success factors in agile software projects', *The Journal of Systems and Software*, vol. 81, pp.961–971.

Despa, ML 2014, 'Comparative study on software development methodologies', *Database Systems Journal*, vol.5, no.3, pp.37 - 56.

Eason, OK 2016, 'Information Systems Development Methodologies Transitions: An Analysis of Waterfall to Agile Methodology', Honors Thesis, University of New Hampshire, Durham.

Gheni, AY, Jusoh, YY, Jabar, MA, & Ali, MN 2017, 'The Critical Success Factors (CSFs) for IT Projects', *Journal of Telecommunication, Electronic and Computer Engineering*, vol.9, no.3, pp. 13-17.

Habib, Z 2009, 'The Critical Success Factors in Implementation of Software Process Improvement Efforts: CSFs, Motivators & Obstacles', Master Thesis, University of Gothenburg, Gothenburg.

Kulathunga, D & Ratiyala, SD. 2018, 'Key Success Factors of Scrum Software Development Methodology in Sri Lanka', *American Scientific Research Journal for Engineering, Technology, and Sciences (ASRJETS)*, vol. 45, no.1, pp. 234 -252.

Laudon, KC & Laudon JP 2014, *Management Information Systems- Managing the Digital Firm*, Pearson Education, New Jersey.

Mohagheghi, P & Jorgensen, M 2017, 'What Contributes to the Success of IT Projects? An Empirical Study of IT Projects in the Norwegian Public Sector', *Journal of Software*, vol.12, no.9, pp.751- 758.

Nah, FFH & Delgado, S 2006, 'Critical Success Factors for Enterprise Resource Planning Implementation and Upgrade', *Journal of Computer Information Systems*, vol.45, no.5, pp. 99-113.

Picek, R 2009, 'Suitability of Modern Software Development Methodologies for Model-Driven Development', *Journal of Information and Organizational Sciences*, vol.33, no.2, pp.285-295.

Rainer, A & Hall, T (2003), 'A quantitative and qualitative analysis of factors affecting software processes'. *Journal of Systems and Software*, vol.66, no.1, pp. 7-21.